

Plasmonic induced effect of Au-graphene-TiO₂ photocatalyst for visible region solar water splitting

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Abstract

Plasmonic Au loaded reduced graphene oxide (rGOs)-TiO₂ photocatalysts were synthesized by using hydrothermal decomposition processes. The graphene oxides (GOs: 0.25-1.0 wt%), Au (1.0-4.0 wt%) and rest TiO₂ were chosen to prepare the Au loaded rGO-TiO₂ photocatalysts. The formation of GOs is confirmed by the observation of D- and G-band peaks at around 1352 and 1596 cm⁻¹ in Raman spectrum. The Au nanoparticles loaded on rGO-TiO₂ surface are around 5 nm as observed in TEM. The photocatalytic activity critically depends on the catalyst architecture. The pure TiO₂ evolved small amount of H₂, i.e., 0.58 mmol, whereas the mixing of small amount of GOs (0.5 wt%) in TiO₂ enhanced the value of H₂ evolution up to 1.02 mmol. The maximum value of 1.34 mmol H₂ was obtained in 1.0 wt% rGOs-TiO₂ photo-catalyst in comparison to 0.58 mmol for pure TiO₂. The Au loading further effectively enhanced the H₂ production and 2.0 wt% Au loading on 1.0 wt% rGOs-TiO₂ surface evolved maximum 12.18 mmol of H₂. The enhanced value of H₂ supports that rGOs and Au successfully restrains the recombination rate of reductive electrons and oxidative holes of highly crystalline TiO₂ for efficient H₂ production.

Keywords: Plasmonic, TiO₂, Water Splitting, Gold